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RESOURCE USE AND COLONY PERFORMANCE
OF HONEY BEES IN FOREST LANDSCAPES

*Uso delle risorse e performance delle colonie delle api da miele
in paesaggi forestali*

Natural forests have been the main habitat of wild-living, native populations of the Western honey bee *Apis mellifera* L. in Europe (REQUIER *et al.*, 2019). Centuries-long human modification of forest landscapes across Europe, driven by deforestation, exploitation forestry, and expanding agriculture and settlement areas have tremendously changed habitat conditions for feral honey bee populations. Nowadays, only very low densities of wild-living colonies are found in German forests, and it is debated whether permanent populations of wild-living colonies can still persist (KOHL & RUTSCHMANN, 2018). Across Europe, the densities of forest-dwelling wild colonies are expected to vary widely due to variation in forest type (e.g. coniferous versus deciduous or managed versus unmanaged forests) and forest size (REQUIER *et al.*, 2020). A recent study from northern Spain shows that hibernation success of wild honey bee colonies is increasing in landscapes with a high proportion of natural or semi-natural habitats (RUTSCHMANN *et al.*, 2022).

However, we currently lack knowledge about the factors that limit the survival and performance of wild-living honey bee colonies in forests. Main factors to consider are the availability of nesting places, the impact of parasites and pathogens and the quantity, quality and continuity of floral resources provided by forests. A fascinating method to reveal the spatial distribution and temporal turnover of the most rewarding pollen and nectar resources used by honey bee colonies is the decoding of so-called bee dances (VISSCHER & SEELEY, 1982). Most studies on foraging distances

and habitat preferences of honeybee colonies have been performed in central European agricultural landscapes (STEFFAN-DEWENTER & KUHN, 2003, DANNER *et al.* 2016). These studies indicate that honeybees prefer semi-natural grassland whereas non-flowering crops and forests were those habitats with lowest visitation rates per observation time and area (DANNER *et al.*, 2016). Interestingly, colonies showed an increasingly strong preference for semi-natural grassland habitats with diverse pollen resources in landscapes dominated by agriculture (DANNER *et al.*, 2016). However, comparable studies in landscapes dominated by forests are lacking so far. RUTSCHMANN *et al.* (submitted) performed a field experiment in southern Germany (Steigerwald, Lower Franconia) to explore the resource use and performance of honeybee colonies in forest landscapes differing in the proportion and composition of forest habitats. They decoded bee dances to unravel the spatial and temporal distribution of floral resources in the landscape, took regular pollen samples which were identified via metabarcoding to characterise the origin of pollen resources (DANNER *et al.*, 2017), and continuously monitored colony weight as a measure of colony performance. In forest landscapes differing in the proportion of forest between 50-99% they found a significant increase in mean foraging distances with increasing forest cover and stronger effects of forest cover on foraging distances for pollen than for nectar, indicating that pollen resources were more limiting in forest habitats. Seasonal variation in foraging distances and general preferences for non-forest habitats such as grasslands, arable crops and settlement areas suggest that forest habitats do not provide sufficient year-round resources for honeybee colonies. In conclusion, the value of managed central European forests as habitat for honey bees could be significantly increased by the continuous provision of floral resources during the whole season. To promote wild-living honey bee colonies and other wild pollinators, the diversification of forest stands with insect-pollinated trees, shrubs, forest gaps with herbaceous flowering plants, and, at larger spatial scales, the management of landscapes with high habitat diversity is recommended.

REFERENCES

- DANNER N., KELLER A., HÄRTEL S. & STEFFAN-DEWENTER I., 2017. Honey bee foraging ecology: Season but not landscape diversity shapes the amount and diversity of collected pollen. *PLOS ONE*, 12: e0183716.
- DANNER N., MOLITOR A.M., SCHIELE S., HÄRTEL S. & STEFFAN DEWENTER I., 2016. Season and landscape composition affect pollen foraging distances and habitat use of honey bees. *Ecol. Appl.*, 26: 1920–1929.

- KOHL P.L. & RUTSCHMANN B., 2018. The neglected bee trees: European beech forests as a home for feral honey bee colonies. *PeerJ* 6: e4602.
- REQUIER F., GARNERY L., KOHL P.L., NJOVU H.K., PIRK C.W., CREWE R.M. & STEFFAN-DEWENTER I., 2019. The conservation of native honey bees is crucial. *Trends Ecol. & Evol.*, 34: 789-798.
- REQUIER F., PAILLET Y., LAROCHE F., RUTSCHMANN B., ZHANG J., LOMBARDI F., SVOBODA M. & STEFFAN-DEWENTER I., 2020. Contribution of European forests to safeguard wild honeybee populations. *Conserv. Lett.*, 13: e12693.
- RUTSCHMANN B., KOHL P.L., MACHADO A. & STEFFAN-DEWENTER I., 2022. Semi-natural habitats promote winter survival of wild-living honeybees in an agricultural landscape. *Biol. Conserv.*, 266: 109450.
- RUTSCHMANN B., KOHL P.L. & STEFFAN-DEWENTER I., 2023. Foraging distances, habitat preferences and seasonal colony performance of honey bees in Central European forest landscapes. *J Appl Ecol*, DOI: 10.1111/1365-2664.14389.
- STEFFAN-DEWENTER I. & KUHN A., 2003. Honeybee foraging in differentially structured landscapes. *Proc. R. Soc. B*, 270: 569-575.
- VISSCHER K.P. & SEELEY T.D., 1982. Foraging strategy of honeybee colonies in a temperate deciduous forest. *Ecology*, 63: 1790–1801.

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